

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting; Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher, Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University

Md. Anowar Hossain

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

(E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>)

Cite: *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain*, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace in PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency in higher education, first version submitted to Nobel committee for Nobel nomination in 2023 under affiliation of RMIT University; *School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia*; 26 November 2024.

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Keynote of invention at PhD school for the peace of PhD schooling

This is a PhD harassment report to pursue PhD (Fashion & Textiles). This harassment thesis is entitled "Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's invention for the peace of PhD schooling for the peace of mankind for the excellency of higher education to pursue PhD (Fashion & Textiles) entitled Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds". This PhD is funded by Australian Government RTP stipend scholarship. This PhD is also self-funded and self-invested around 1800000 USD (in words eighteen lakh USD) under Australian compliance of salary of resource person category, PhD researcher category, technologist category, scientist category and professor category. This part of

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PhD harassment of PhD (Fashion & Textiles) has contribution on criminology, sociology, international law, education and PhD research.

Every PhD school is an ethical platform to achieve a PhD degree. PhD education, PhD scholarship, PhD research and PhD achievement are the vibrant segment for the society development, society contribution and invention for the peace of mankind all over the world. Human brain engineering in PhD platform, researcher practices, PhD practices, professor practices, scientist practices and technological inventions are the quality dedication for the peace of mankind. These are the symptoms for increasing of human life time in terms of quality surviving. Safety of researchers, safety of scientists is the global challenge for the right motivation of invention and inventors. The conspiracy of life-threatening, hidden life-threatening, PhD harassment and PhD corruption are the obstacle of quality PhD education in an ethical platform of PhD schooling when a PhD researcher invest their 'young time' for a PhD degree. PhD researcher gets a minimum amount of honorary salary in the name of PhD scholarship. The case letters of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in PhD journey have significant contribution for every consideration of quality PhD schooling. PhD school may influence for highest climbing and highest platform for global standardization of global PhD schooling. The conspiracy of hidden life-threatening, unethical PhD suspension, unethical cancellation of PhD enrolment has been practically exemplified and focused to eliminate PhD obstacle at PhD school. In this author contribution, the PhD struggling and the PhD journey have new contribution for PhD researchers and PhD supervisors for practicing an ethical PhD in PhD school. This is an academic platform of Australian PhD school at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. A real-life history of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school have been signified, coalesced and published for society contribution and self-protection of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD researcher at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University investigated officially with author's family office in home country (Bangladesh) of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under verbal declaration and threatening at PhD school. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye of PhD school also communicated with former academic office of author and former professional office of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain in home and abroad under verbal declaration and threatening at PhD school. Accordingly, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye of PhD school also communicated with ambulance team of PhD candidate. Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye also communicated with emergency medical team of PhD candidate in St. Vincent hospital in Melbourne, Australia. The misuse of cyber technology also used for personal monitoring of PhD researcher in PhD school. This philosophy of critical conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment has direct impact for the protection of whole mankind, especially for the peace in PhD schooling, criminology, sociology. The misuse of brain engineering in a prestigious PhD research platform and the misuse

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Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

of technology in a prestigious PhD research platform are the artificial warning sign of academic and professional crime which are significantly stated against the peace of PhD schooling against the global ethics of brain engineering. Definitely, every schooling platform is being expanded and expanded in a global platform for civilized nature of human being. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain had a lot of reporting for conspiracy of life-threatening in Australian PhD school, PhD harassment, academic and professional motivation, for the peace of mankind, for the peace of global PhD schooling. Subsequently, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain notified about his family office, former academic office and delegates, RMIT University to satisfy Australian Quality of Research Framework in PhD school to satisfy the verbal order of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and Professor Dr. Lijing Wang in prestigious PhD school, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Therefore, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University tried to kill Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD candidate. Hence, Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye also tried to robber intellectual property of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. This is an official environment of PhD Schooling in an official & ethical platform of teaching-learning and brain engineering action of Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye.

Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain is a study addicted person from child schooling to PhD schooling. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066 has been completed PhD requirement by sole-author PhD research & sole-author PhD publication, supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang & Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain continued his full time PhD research, his full scholarship period PhD research at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Md. Anowar Hossain faced conspiracy of life-threatening in Melbourne in PhD school. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye acted as planning director, conspiracy director, financial director, trafficking director and executive director for killing conspiracy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was able to present and submit a complete PhD thesis for his confirmation of PhD candidature in 2020-2021. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye also announced 'Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University on behalf of Martin G. Bean, Former Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, year 2020-2021. Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain successfully completed the requirements of his PhD (Fashion & Textiles) concentrated on color engineering, camouflage engineering and camouflage textiles. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye tried to kill PhD candidate, tried to cease intellectual property of PhD candidate, tried to kill the PhD dream and tried to kill the self-motivation of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain under an official act of hidden life-threatening in Australian PhD school. Dr.

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also studied and practiced on PhD in criminology at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when he defended against the official act of hidden life-threatening at PhD school under the registered PhD research on PhD (Fashion & Textiles). The life-threatening history was officially notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University and whole concern of RMIT University, whole concern of Australian Community under Australian Quality of Research Framework. The PhD degree was accomplished under non-compliance harassment & motivation such as completed first milestone & second milestone without revision and negative comments under congratulation and positive comments, number of action & support-2, artificial hampering of PhD progress, verbal threatening & PhD harassment in different way, continuous conspiracy of life-threatening of Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, unethical executive suspension, psychologist bullying in PhD school, 100% neglecting of life-threatening bullying of Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD school connection with psychologist, immoral cancellation of PhD enrolment and forwarded to Victorian Ombudsman; Dr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to Victorian police station, reported to national security of Australia, reported to Australian Institute of Criminology, reported to Australian Federal Police, reported to country court of Australia, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to high court of Australia, reported to Australian Bar association, reported to Australian education department, reported to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government, reported to the minister and delegates of Australian home affairs, reported to Australian foreign affairs, reported to Victoria legal aid, reported to Australian Competition and Consumer Commission, reported to international human rights, different related organizations, Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to fight with Australian court due to financial hardship, submitted to the Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat, submitted to the office of Australian high commissioner to Bangladesh, high commissioner of Bangladesh to Australia, Governor-General of the Commonwealth of Australia, the Honourable David Hurley AC DSC (Retd), submitted to nobel organization for nobel nomination about life-threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain. Unfortunately, life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue was intentionally converted to the cancellation of material approval for PhD research & PhD progress-2021, high risk misconduct, executive suspension-2022, psychologist bullying-2023 and cancellation of PhD enrolment-2023. A full scholarship payment was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of research allowance was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of time allowance was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of scholarly allowance was not provided to PhD candidate. Hence, paid scholarship was around 252666AUD including tuition/professor's fees, nonpaid scholarship was around 36426AUD and nonpaid salary was around 249209AUD for artificial financial harassment of research progress at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain self-invested around 1800000 USD (in words eighteen lakh USD) for his self-sacrifice and self-earning under Australian Compliance in Australian PhD School in Australia. 50% income support and 100% life-

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International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

safety support for compensations were requested and proposed to Vice Chancellor, RMIT University for 63 years duration under calculation of 100 years life-time of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain. 9450000USD (in words ninety-four lakhs and fifty thousand USD) was proposed and requested for 50% income support compensation. 22680000USD (in words two crore twenty-six lakhs and eighty thousand USD) was proposed and requested for 100% life-safety compensation. Every correspondence of PhD contribution, conspiracy of life threatening, PhD harassment was forwarded to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice chancellor, RMIT University (vc@rmit.edu.au), school office and all concern offices at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Occurrence and motivation of PhD schooling was also mentioned in the article of “Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform”. This report is a PhD schooling harassment at RMIT University under proceeding to the registry of High Court of Australia, recommended/insinuated by the Victorian ombudsman of Australia, RMIT University of Australia and Department of Education, Government of Australia. High of court of Australia is also making a legal cost harassment to PhD candidate. Therefore, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is asking to Australian high court to pay 8390000 Australian penalty unit (230,72,50,000AUD). (Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023f, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o) (Hossain, 2023b, 2023e, 2023g, 2023h, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023t; Hossain, 2023d, 2023e; Hossain, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023af, 2023ag; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024r) (Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023f, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024r) (Hossain, 2023a, 2023h, 2023i, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023u; Hossain, 2023a, 2023b; Hossain, 2023v, 2023w; Hossain, 2023c; Hossain, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac; Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; Hossain, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024s, 2024t; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024).

[All readers are being highly requested to understand the whole philosophy of attachments (a case report) without considering and understanding specific word or sentence; explained for whole meaning under additional output of PhD Degree in PhD school, school of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University]

Keywords: PhD education, PhD research, PhD school, PhD obstacle, PhD harassment, PhD corruption, PhD struggling, society contribution, family struggling for education, PhD struggling, peace in PhD schooling, Dress code, life-threatening conspiracy in Australian PhD school

Publication, public presentation and peer review process related to Anowar Hossain's invention of peace in PhD schooling

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain faced hidden conspiracy of life threatening and notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor and delegate, RMIT University
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33536.61441>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8317924>

Hossain, M. A. (2023h). *Dress code from primary schooling to PhD schooling, harassment, motivation and understanding in an international education platform*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23508.78724/2>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023i). *Invitation of PhD Researchers in international platform for global peace of mankind. a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. A.* Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, engr.anowar@yahoo.com.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19237.88800>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268846>

Hossain, M. A. (2023j). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my family/relative peoples for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-3)*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19378.38089>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970344>

Hossain, M. A. (2023k). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my maternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-1).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16475.13603/1>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970310>

Hossain, M. A. (2023l). *My family struggling from my child schooling to PhD schooling; communication and relation with my paternal family for my life-threatening investigation during my PhD schooling at RMIT University in Australia (Part-2).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29896.90887>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10970241>

Hossain, M. A. (2023m). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-01).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16530.84162>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890974>

Hossain, M. A. (2023n). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-02).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23241.72807>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892431>

Hossain, M. A. (2023o). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-03).*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10134.52802>;

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913011>

Hossain, M. A. (2023p). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-04)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27336.08962>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8047201>

Hossain, M. A. (2023q). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-05)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.23045.93929>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8137396>

Hossain, M. A. (2023r). *My PhD struggling, hidden life-threatening, a tragedy and announcement of Nobel Nominee at PhD School (Part-06)*.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27723.57120>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146631>

Hossain, M. A. (2023s). *Non-paid salary of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University submitted for approval of Professor Dr. Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27962.16328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10132457>

Hossain, M. A. (2023t). *PhD scholarship is an honour of a PhD candidate, PhD scholarship is comparatively lower paid job, PhD scholarship is a self-sacrifice and future investment for achieving a quality PhD degree in a quality schooling platform.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21433.34402>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747607>

Hossain, M. A. (2023u). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking necessary action by the Australian crime commission act (ACC), 2002; 7A, 7C and/or relevant act of criminal investigation in PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26327.04002>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10116196>

Hossain, M. A. (2023a). *Plaintiff, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist; School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, PhD ID: 3820066 is seeking free of cost legal action to high court of Australia and/or fully funded PhD Scholarship for every cost of high court of Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27057.76642>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10182345>

Hossain, M. A. (2023b). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Bangladeshi Passport No: EE0444946; Bangladeshi Address: Vill: Purbo Nuthurchar, P.O: K. Mohonpur (Postal Code: 1990) P.S: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh is reporting life-threatening conspiracy to Mr. Jeremy Bruer, Australian High Commissioner to Bangladesh located at 184 Gulshan Avenue, Gulshan, Dhaka, Bangladesh.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28153.24164>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025287>

23 November 2024

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Hossain, M. A. (2023v). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is expected for full-time/part-time/contractual/casual positions of professional services all over the world.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13240.32001>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360586>

Hossain, M. A. (2023w). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is seeking legal support to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP, Prime Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in PhD school, RMIT University.* Page | 9
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19140.19849>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10990583>

Hossain, M. A. (2023c). *Reporting and filing to High Court of Australia for court hearing & court writ of life-threatening conspiracy to kill PhD researcher and artificial killing conspiracy of PhD dream of a PhD scholar in a prestigious platform of PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20689.30567>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10986579>

Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>

Hossain, M. A. (2023e). *Reporting to Honorable Minister, Department of Home Affairs, Australia and delegates for activation and extension of VISA of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University until the final order of Australian Supreme Court, Australian human rights commission and chief authorities of Australian Government relates to PhD harassment and conspiracy of life-threatening of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21520.17927>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195451>

Hossain, M. A. (2023x). *Reporting to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus*

Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

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Hossain, M. A. (2023y). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Hossain, M. A. (2023z). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023aa). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>

Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023ab). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ac). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>

Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street,

23 November 2024

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
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 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ad). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ae). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

Hossain, M. A. (2023af). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ag). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WXVkgicfKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

- Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208048>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of ‘free of cost google drive (2TB) access’ to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the ‘Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)’ under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and*

23 November 2024

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

500.211,1994.

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The author is self-declaring the sole-authorship of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD, Defence Scientist in terms of conceptualization, visualization, resource, self-supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, planning and prediction, analysis, writing the original draft, manuscript editing, and publication process. The scholarship or funder has no scholarly role of the design of research, research idea or visualization, drafting of manuscript, editing of manuscript, and publication of manuscript.

23 November 2024

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Acknowledgement

Sole author, director (PhD research), director (defence project) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist; Name of Father: Late Dr. Md. Abdur Rashid, Medical Practitioner; Permanent Residence (PR): Village: Purbo Nuthurchar, Post Office: K. Mohonpur (1990), Police Station: Gopalpur, District: Tangail, Dhaka, Bangladesh, South Asia (PR by birth); Nationality, National ID, Passport and Birth Registration Number: 19862692620993890, A15988852/EE0444946/AF3831770, 003236; PhD (Doctor of Philosophy) application ID: 2612540, PhD student ID: 3820066, Program Name: DR213, PhD (Fashion and Textiles), School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia; Lecturer on Textile Engineering (study leave), Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Birulia, Savar-1340, Dhaka, Bangladesh acknowledges RMIT University and the Australian government for funding through research training program (RTP) stipend scholarship, 2020-2024. Author, Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>) also acknowledges 'Professor Dr. Lijing Wang' (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7300-9271>) and 'Emeritus Professor Dr. Robert Shanks' (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3790-5148>), School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University for their supervision works in the PhD school. This writing for mankind was accidentally generated during PhD Journey of author at PhD school when author faced hidden life-threatening at PhD school by Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye at PhD school.

A short summary and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>

Glossaries

Official act of hidden life-threatening: An ethical platform of PhD schooling where unethical activities and occurrence of official life-threatening was executed by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and officially supported to Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye by silence by silence.

Family office: An office of home when professional office in PhD school was avoided due to critical conspiracy of life-threatening, planned & chief executed by Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye and officially supported to Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye by silence by silence.

26 November 2024

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

Signature

Office of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist;
PhD student ID: 3820066, 512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, RMIT University,
Melbourne, Vic-3056, The Commonwealth of Australia.

E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

If necessary, please visit the following link for author information about Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist; Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

23 November 2024

Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, MTech
PhD Researcher, ID: 3820066
(Funded by Australian Government Scholarship)
School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University
512.01.12, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick
Vic-3056, Australia.

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<http://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT
<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/author/record/JMP-7353-2023>
<https://sciprofiles.com/profile/1995474>

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23 November 2024

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
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 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
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 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anwar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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Anowar

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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23 November 2024

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist PhD Engg. (RMIT, Australia), MTech (CU, India), BSc Engg. (CU, Bangladesh) Professor and Engineer (R&D) in Technical Textiles, Dyeing & Processing Australian Government Award Winner (RTP Stipend Scholarship, 2020)
 Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University
 PhD (Technical Textiles & Textile Coloration); PhD Research ID: 3820066
 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
 Former PhD Researcher (Part time), Department of Chemistry Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
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 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>;
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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoc Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engranowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>

Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>

Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>*

Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>

- Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8182709>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cc). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>
- Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cd). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ce). *Self-declared certificate on Scientist (Camouflage Physics) (Australia Patent No. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13103.71848>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). *A short summery and evidences of Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship for Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14593.43368>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12722555>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). *Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions. School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>

23 November 2024

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 School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia
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 MTech in Textile Technology (Technical Textiles)
 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ck). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>

Hossain, M. A. (2023cl). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-02)*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24105.98403>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162633>; <https://youtu.be/0WVXkigicKg>

Hossain, M. A. (2024a). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10964382>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of “Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist” on “Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds”* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street,

- Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208048>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14048863>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13994976>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India*.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>
- Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent*

23 November 2024

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
<www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT>

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Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264 engranowar06@gmail.com

residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11516770>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19343.76968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Hossain, M. A. (2024w). *Nobel Nominee, RMIT University, Camouflage physics; color engineering versus camouflage engineering for defence protection* [Biodata].

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14217868>

Hossain, M. A. (2024x). *Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

Hossain, M. A. (2024y). *Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>

Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>

Hossain, M. A., & Samanta, A. (2018). *Green Dyeing On Cotton Fabric Demodulated From Diospyros Malabarica and Camellia Sinensis with Green Mordanting Agent. Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 2(2), 1-8.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.32474/LTTFD.2018.02.000132>

Hossain, M. A., Samanta, A., Abser, M. N., & Dilruba, F. A. (2019). *A Review on Technological and Natural Dyeing Concepts for Natural Dyeing along with Natural Finishing on Natural*

Acad

23 November 2024

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 Dept. of Jute and Fibre Technology, Institute of Jute Technology University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India
 BSc in Textile Engineering, Department of Textile Engineering, Faculty of Science & Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh
International Research Consultant (Textile Coloration, Textile & Chemical Processing, Technical Textiles, Textile Engineering, Cost Minimization in Textile Industry, R & D in Textile Industry, Geotextiles, Defence Textiles, Defence Materials, Defence Research Organization of Army, Navy, Air force and Police, Public Service/Crime/Crisis/Textile Commission, PhD/PostDoe Researcher, Course Curriculum of Higher Degree, Law, Criminology, Human Rights, Judge Court, High Court, Supreme Court, Ministry/Minister/President/Governor/King of any country, Textile/Defence/Law/Home ministry, Parliament/Government of any country, Crime Protection, Crime Investigation, Cyber Crime, Crime analysis & Reporting, Crime in Higher Education, Quality in Higher Education, Journal & News, Entrepreneur); Motivational speaker; literary & Science writer; Philosopher; Specialized Trainer of Certificate Courses in BSc Engg, MTech, PhD Engg
Visit Profile for more details about Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD: Scientist
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>
www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

Professor, Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world since 6 July 2022; Australia Lecturer (Study Leave), Department of Textile Engineering City University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Professor & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, BCMC College of Engineering & Technology, Jessore; Affiliated by University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head of the Department, Department of Textile Engineering, Newcastle University College (NUC)
 Former Assistant Registrar (Examination), NUC, Chittagong; Affiliated by University of Chittagong, Bangladesh
 Former Chief Executive Officer, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikunja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Product Developer & Coordinator (Textile Printing), Gothic Design Ltd, Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assistant Merchandiser (Garments & Fashion), Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (Research & Development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, Examination Committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh.
 Specialized Training on Textile Technology (Bangladesh, India, Australia)
Research Address since 2020: 512. 01. 12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia
Contact: E-mail: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; Mobile: +8801788396264
engranowar06@gmail.com

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